

**Multisensory signs for accessibility and safety
in tourism and leisure time offers**

= Short Version =

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Introduction

GATE – “Granting Accessible Tourism for Everyone” or “Inclusive tourism is good for all”. In the light of this principle, the purpose of the GATE project is to substantially contribute in the improvement of tourism offers for people with disabilities. This document provides an overview of the signs and symbols using which accessibility and multisensory signage for accessible tourism, subjected to examination in the various GATE-linked studies (see GATE 2020a/b), have been encoded. Multisensory signage refers to the whole sector of communication of information regarding tourism and leisure time, thereby increasing the safety of people with disabilities.

While precise guidelines have already been defined regarding the setting up of barrier-free hotel structures and have been confirmed by law, not much attention has been paid to making equally accessible the local tourist areas and destinations as well (Aigner et al., 2015; Lorenz & Melzer, 2013). Increasingly more often, it is the destinations that invest effort and money in making outdoor areas more accessible. As regards signage and multimedia support, reference is mainly made to local customary systems. Lack of information or the fact that information is represented or positioned inadequately is often the main reason which disabled persons do not feel at ease in nature, even in structures considered to be accessible.

Symbols for indicating accessibility

Back in the 1960’s, attempts had been made to create symbols for accessibility. Due to the lack of precise agreements, however, the symbols used could be quite different from one another. Often, in order to illustrate accessibility, the promoters of tourism and leisure time offers would use the wheelchair symbol. In this manner, however, people with hearing or sight impairments could not be certain that the structure also met their specific accessibility requirements. As seen by Domínguez et al. (2013), there are no systematic collections of symbols representing accessibility.

When creating symbols representing accessibility, it would be necessary anyhow to make sure people are represented in an as neutral way as possible, for example as regards gender and external features. Moreover, the symbols should have strong contrast. While, according to

ÖNORM B1600:2017-04-01, § 8.2.1¹, white symbols on a black background, or black on yellow, or black on white, or black on blue, or white on blue, or black on white should be considered, in the case of signs the red/green combination should be avoided. The examples given below show symbols for each category involved, without any single one being considered more adequate than the others.

Limitation of mobility:

Walking and hand disabilities:

Autonomously practicable pathway:

Practicable with assistance:

Hard-of-hearing people:

Assisted listening systems available:

Deaf people:

Information in adequate formats:

Information given via sign language:

Sight-impaired people:

¹ The Austrian guidelines ÖNORM B1600:2017-04-01 can be downloaded for a fee at https://shop.austrian-standards.at/action/de/public/details/597955/OENORM_B_1600_2017_04_01

² Sources: www.parcorossi.it; www.anatom5.de; www.bereit-fuer-barrierefreiheit.eu; ÖNORM A 3011-3, Symbol 55.

³ Sources: www.parcorossi.it; www.reisen-fuer-alle.de; www.anatom5.de; ÖNORM A 3011-3 Symbol; Domínguez et al. 2013.

⁴ Source: <http://www.bereit-fuer-barrierefreiheit.eu>

⁵ Sources: www.reisen-fuer-alle.de; ÖNORM B 1600; Domínguez et al., 2013; www.anatom5.de

⁶ Source: www.induktionsschleife.at; www.anatom5.de

⁷ Source: ÖNORM B1600:2017-04-01, § 8 (see above).

⁸ Sources: www.parcorossi.it; www.anatom5.de; www.holidaysonwheels.at

⁹ Sources: www.reisen-fuer-alle.de, www.bereit-fuer-barrierefreiheit.eu, www.oeglb.at, Domínguez et al. 2013.

¹⁰ Sources: www.reisen-fuer-alle.de; www.bereit-fuer-barrierefreiheit.eu; www.anatom5.de

Blind people:		11
Persons with learning disabilities:		12

Table 1: Symbols for indicating accessibility

Multisensory signs

Multisensory signs play a key role in setting up accessible structures. In order to develop them adequately for each category, when creating the signage and guide system one should consider the different needs of people with disabilities. The following table shows several examples of different needs for each form of limitation:

Limitation of mobility:		
Walking and hand disabilities:	- Gentle slopes - Handrails - Rest areas	- Low muscle engagement - Easy to use - Sitting available
Persons using wheelchairs	- Parking for the disabled - Stable flooring - Possible absence of steps	- Ramps - Accessible WCs - Adequate turning space
Hard-of-hearing people:	- Good acoustics - Low background noise	- Information with images and text - Assisted listening systems
Deaf people:	- Sign language - Visual information	- Good lighting - Visual contact (lips)
Sight-impaired people:	- Clear pathway indications - Handrail - Easy to read signs	- No obstacles - Good lighting - Audio information
Blind people:	- Tactile paths - Ground surface indicators	- Audio information - Tactile information
People with learning disabilities:	- Simple language - Guided trails (colours)	- Easily understandable signage - Absence of dangerous spots

Table 2: Needs of people with disabilities

¹¹ Sources: www.reisen-fuer-alle.de; www.bereit-fuer-barrierefreiheit.eu; www.anatom5.de; www.holidaysonwheels.at; ÖNORM V 2106; Domínguez et al. 2013.

¹² Sources: www.reisen-fuer-alle.de; www.bereit-fuer-barrierefreiheit.eu; www.euregio-barrierefrei.eu; www.capito.eu; Domínguez et al. 2013.

Luckily, already many areas and providers of tourist services are strongly committed to setting up accessible natural sites using multisensory signage. Table 3 is based on the needs of people with disabilities as described above and offers 20 examples of such signals. Divided into 14 ‘analogic’ multisensory signs and 6 ‘digital’ signs, it also shows symbols to be used for specific disabilities. The categories for which the solution is especially suited are highlighted (framed).

Analogic signage

Multisensory information boards

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Tactile information boards in excursion areas and along trails

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Touchable sculptures

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Direction-indicating objects

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Tactile paths and ground surface indicators

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¹³ Arnade & Heiden (2002).

¹⁴ Erlensee natural park (Arnade & Heiden 2002).

¹⁵ Kaunergrat natural park - “3000 m VERTICAL”, <https://www.kaunergrat.at/de/erlebnis/naturparkhaus/>

¹⁶ Parco Rossi: ARAC kite as indicator, <http://www.parcorossi.it>

¹⁷ Parco Rossi: Tactile paths and ground surface indicators, <http://www.parcorossi.it>

Analogic signage

Tree trunks as path indicators

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Tactile elements on ground surfaces

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Braille writing on handrails

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Braille writing integrated in handrails

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Braille writing on doors

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Large and high-contrast writing

23

Road signs with incisions

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¹⁸ Arnade & Heiden (2002).

¹⁹ Patscherkofel: Das Kofel restaurant (picture: KMU & Tourismus, University of Innsbruck)

²⁰ Virgen: Trail of perceptions, https://www.meinbezirk.at/osttirol/c-lokales/der-weg-der-sinne_a3264687

²¹ ÖZIV Bundesverband, <https://www.oeziv.org/access/wissenswertes-ueber-umfassende-barrierefreiheit/>

²² Patscherkofel: Das Kofel, restaurant (Picture: KMU & Tourismus, University of Innsbruck).

²³ Patscherkofel: Downhill station area (Picture: KMU & Tourismus, University of Innsbruck).

²⁴ Hainich national park, <https://www.nationalpark-hainich.de/de.html>

Analogic signage

Mid-height information boards

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Barriers at entrance to areas

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Digital signage

Digital information boards

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Client-facing screen on cash registers

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Multimedia guides

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²⁵ Dachstein – UNESCO World Heritage view: Panoramic panel, <https://dachstein-salzkammergut.com/de/sommer/oberirdisch/welterbeblick/>

²⁶ Patscherkofel: Downhill station, entrance (Picture: KMU & Tourismus, University of Innsbruck).

²⁷ 4xperts: Projects & Examples, <https://www.4xperts.de/projekte-beispiele>

²⁸ SDS cash register systems, <https://www.sds-kassensysteme.de/touchscreen/>

²⁹ Parco Rossi, <http://www.parcorossi.it>

Digital signage

iBeacons

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App Talking Trails

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Virtual reality

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Table 3: Set of multisensory symbols

Summary

This part of the study refers to signs (symbols and pictograms) used for signalling offers intended for people with various kinds of limitations. Using multisensory signs, it is also possible to organize areas, analogic signage and information boards, as well as multimedia devices (screens, audio- and video-guides) in such a way as to adapt them to the needs of all of the various groups of interest.

³⁰ Parco Rossi, <http://www.parcorossi.it>

³¹ CAI Alpago (Picture: Information materials by GATE partners).

³² VR headset (Picture: KMU & Tourismus, University of Innsbruck).

References

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